

Internship Report

Exploring the representation of Prydz Bay dense water in NEMO CMIP6 models

Submitted by

Jacquemine Delfieu
Gap year (between M1 and M2)
AgroParisTech

Under the guidance of

Dr. Clara Burgard and Dr. Katherine Hutchinson

Laboratoire d'Océanographie et du Climat :
Expérimentations et Approches Numériques

EQUIPE NEMO R&D

Sorbonne Université
From February 3th to July 31st 2025

Highlights

- Even though models do not explicitly simulate ocean-ice shelf interactions, 3 out of 6 models present waters that could correspond to AABW precursors
- None of the models transform waters in the range of density that could correspond to shelf waters, given the definition of HSSW and AABW
- Over-active convection and absence of ocean-ice shelf interaction appear to be the main reasons affecting dense water realism

Abstract

Models can help fill in the gaps in our understanding of oceanic processes in both space and time, in areas where harsh sampling conditions have impeded our ability to have extensive observations. This is the case for Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) formation processes, occurring in four main regions in the Southern Ocean. In these areas, its precursors mix, overflow the continental shelf break and sink to the seafloor to then form AABW. In this study, we investigate dense water properties in one of these regions, Prydz Bay, in the NEMO family of CMIP6 models. We both compare model output with available observations and conduct a cross-comparison between models. We notably look at the properties associated with the representation of dense water, with processes linked to dense water formation, their subsequent export and the transformation of surface waters to dense shelf waters. Results show that without the presence of interactive ice shelves, it is very challenging to correctly represent the parent waters of AABW in coupled climate models. In terms of water mass realism, the models that have paid attention to how the freshwater flux linked to ice shelf melt is represented are able to do a better job compared to observations. As CMIP7 is coming up, over-active convection and absence of ocean-ice shelf interaction appear to be the main reasons affecting dense water realism.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Data and methods	4
2.1	Definition of the water mass properties	4
2.2	Numerical models	4
2.3	Observations	5
2.4	Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation Calculation	7
3	Results	9
3.1	Realism of the dense water representation	9
3.2	Processes linked to dense water formation and export	14
3.3	Creation of dense water in the models	18
4	Summary and discussion	25
5	Conclusion and outlook	28
	Appendix	29

Chapter 1

Introduction

Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) is the densest water mass of the global ocean and occupies the abyssal layers, representing 30 to 40 % of the oceanic volume (Jia et al. 2022). The three main precursors of AABW are Ice Shelf Water (ISW), High Salinity Shelf Water (HSSW) and Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), see Figure 1. HSSW is formed due to brine rejection during intense sea ice formation occurring in coastal polynyas. These polynyas are semi-permanent areas of open water and play a key role in dense water production (Mohrmann et al. 2021). CDW is a comparably warm water mass that occasionally intrudes onto the continental shelf, thereby introducing heat into the area and the possibility for the basal and frontal melting of ice shelves. This melt process releases buoyant freshwater, known as ISW that rises from under the ice shelf and mixes with the other shelf water masses. There are four main Southern Ocean regions where the majority of AABW is formed. In these areas, HSSW and ISW mix with CDW, overflow the continental shelf break and sink to the seafloor to then be classified as AABW. The properties of these three parent water masses significantly impact AABW.

Figure 1: Schematic of the features, processes and water masses involved in AABW production.

In this study, we focus on one of the principal AABW formation sites ; located in the Indian Sector of the Southern Ocean : Prydz Bay. We chose this region both out of personal curiosity and due to the fact that it is less widely investigated than the Weddell and Ross Seas in terms of its role in dense water production. This bay is located in the Eastern part of Antarctica. The extent of the study area is from 65 to 85°E and 60 to 70°S (see Figure 2). Among the different regional features, two of them are particularly interesting within the scope of this work. The first one is Cape Darnley polynya, a coastal polynya possessing the second highest yearly sea ice production rate within the four different AABW formation site (Blanckensee et al. 2024). It contributes from 6 to 13% to global AABW production (Blanckensee et al. 2024). The second feature is Amery Ice Shelf, draining approximately 16% of the grounded East Antarctic ice sheet (Post et al. 2014). In terms of bathymetry, the limit between the continental shelf and offshore is on average 600m deep (Figure 2) and so this threshold value is used to delimit these two different zones throughout this study.

Figure 2: a) Location of Prydz Bay region (solid lines) and the other three main AABW formation regions (dotted lines) and b) a zoom-in on Prydz Bay with the number 1 representing the location of Cape Darnley Polynya and 2 indicating the frontal region of Amery Ice Shelf.

Within Prydz Bay, wind and circulation patterns are driven by two separate factors. The first are pressure gradients resulting from large scale forcing and the Coriolis effect. The second, which dominates near Amery Ice Shelf, is the local to regional katabatic wind pattern within the atmospheric boundary layer. Together these factors drive the formation and persistence of polynyas and resulting high production of sea ice, responsible for the formation of HSSW and in this way a portion of the parent waters of AABW.

An additional factor forcing the local circulation is the pattern of the bathymetry (see Figure 2b). For example, the bathymetry plays a key role in controlling the transport

of CDW towards the continental shelf, which in turn influences the basal melt of the ice shelf. Furthermore, bathymetry partly explains the enhanced effect of retaining deep waters within Prydz Bay, the intrusion of CDW or the temperature gradient in Amery Ice Shelf cavity. For example, the Amery Depression located in front of Amery Ice Shelf can reach 1000 m depth (Jin et al. 2024).

In order to investigate the dense water properties in Prydz Bay, several tools can be used. One of them is in-situ sampling. Nevertheless, observations in winter time, during dense water formation seasonal peak, are very sparse, due to the large extent of sea ice posing a challenge for ship-based measurements. One alternative can be satellite observations but these only capture surface conditions. Satellite data is therefore very useful for identifying polynyas but does not enable us to study the ocean beneath.

Models are therefore considered useful tools to explore the evolution of water properties in both time and space, to fill in the gaps in our understanding of oceanic processes in areas where harsh sampling conditions have impeded our ability to have extensive observations. The CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project) aims to provide projections and scenarios to better understand past, present and future climate. Models that participated in its 6th phase, known as CMIP6, belong to the latest release of this project. They are, among other purposes, used to simulate the future of the polar oceans and ice sheets. Although these models are useful to understand oceanic properties, they are often subject to large uncertainties. Regarding their representations of AABW, CMIP6 models present several limitations, leading to uncertainties in global metrics that are key to our understanding of future climate changes (Heuzé, 2021).

In this study, we focus on CMIP6 models that employ the same ocean model component : the NEMO model (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean, Madec et al. 2024). Within this “family” of climate models, ice shelves are represented as a completely closed cavity (part of the coastline). However, the basal melt is in some way accounted for via a parameterized freshwater flux at the ice shelf front. The most sophisticated parameterization used by the NEMO family of CMIP6 models is that developed by Mathiot et al. 2017, which attempts to mimic the overturning circulation under the ice shelf via the introduction of a meltwater flux distributed over the depth range and width of the cavity at the ice shelf front.

Here we explore how the NEMO family of CMIP6 models represents dense water formation and shelf water properties within Prydz Bay, both by comparing model output with available observations and through a cross-comparison between models. We first evaluate the models regarding their aptitude to represent dense water and then endeavor to understand which processes could be responsible for the formation and export of these waters. Finally, we present a deep-dive into the different approaches of climate centers regarding their choices on how to represent high latitude processes and dense water formation.

Chapter 2

Data and methods

2.1 Definition of the water mass properties

In this report, HSSW, ISW and AABW definitions are based on the work of Murakami et al. 2023 and are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: *Regional definitions of the water masses of interest*

Water mass	Temperature (°C)	Salinity	Density (kg.m ⁻³)	Depth (m)
ISW	$\theta < T_f$	-	$\sigma < 27.82$	-
HSSW	$\theta < T_f$	$S > 34.5$	$\sigma \geq 28$	-
AABW	$T_f + 0.1 < \theta < 0.1$	$S > 34.5$	$\sigma > 27.82$	$z < -1000$

2.2 Numerical models

We evaluate seven CMIP6 models, all using the NEMO ocean component, which facilitates their intercomparison, especially when focusing on the simulation of deep oceanic processes.

Table 2 presents the chosen models, the associated climate center that produced the simulations, their resolution and their version of NEMO. We use historical experiment outputs and one ensemble member per model.

We use the ESGF metagrid platform to download various CMIP6 variable files. When one of the models is not displayed on a plot, it means, except for NESM3, that the variable was not available for download.

The ocean variables are potential temperature (thetao), salinity (so), the downward heat flux at seawater surface (hfds), water flux into sea water (wfo), seawater age since surface

contact (*agessc*) and ocean mixed layer depth thickness (*mlotst*). We also use the values of grid-cell area for ocean variables (*areacello*).

The sea ice variables are sea ice area percentage (*siconc*), sea ice mass change through basal growth and through growth in supercooled open water (*sidmassgrowthbot* and *sidmassgrowthwat*) and sea ice thickness (*sithick*).

Table 2: *Models used and characteristics*

Model name	Ensemble member	Ocean component	Horizontal	Vertical	Climate center
CanESM5	r10i1p1f1	NEMO3.4.1	1 x 1	z 45	CCCma
CNRM-CM6-1	r10i1p1f2	NEMO3.6	1 x 1	z*75	CNRM-CERFACS
EC-Earth3	r10i1p1f1	NEMO3.6	1 x 1	z*75	EC-Earth-Consortium
HadGEM3-GC31-LL	r1i1p1f3	NEMO-HadGEM3-GO6.0	1 x 1	z*75	MOHC
IPSL-CM6A-LR	r10i1p1f1	NEMO3.6	1 x 1	z*75	IPSL
NESM3	r1i1p1f1	NEMO3.4	1 x 1	z 46	NUIST
UKESM1-0-LL	r10i1p1f2	NEMO-HadGEM3-GO6.0	1 x 1	z*75	MOHC

2.3 Observations

In order to evaluate the models, we use two types of observations.

Temperature and salinity used as reference are taken from the World Ocean Atlas 2023 product (Locarnini et al. 2024 ; Reagan et al. 2024, respectively). As the number of observations in winter is very low (Figure 3), we base the model evaluation using the WOA 2023 product on summer climatologies.

The second dataset of observations is the “Fifty-year changes of the world ocean’s surface layer in response to climate change”, published by Sallée et al. 2020. It is used to infer reference Mixed Layer Depth thickness values, especially in winter, when the formation of dense water occurs.

Figure 3: *Number of observations at different depth in summer (December - January - February) and Winter (June - July - August). Note the change in the colorbar range between the two seasons.*

2.4 Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation Calculation

Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation (SFWMT) is a measure of overturning circulation, inferred from surface buoyancy (heat and freshwater) fluxes.

The method used for this computation is the one used by Vogt et al. (2024). The calculation of SFWMT values is based on buoyancy fluxes (Eq. 1). Pellichero et al. (2018) define surface buoyancy fluxes as “fluxes received by the ocean surface mixed-layer from atmosphere, ice, and diapycnal mixing”. They have a heat and a freshwater component (Eq. 2).

$$\Psi(\sigma_2) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma_2} B(\sigma_2) \quad (1)$$

$$B(\sigma_2) = -\alpha \frac{Q}{C_p} - \beta \sigma_2 s W \cdot \frac{1}{1-s} \quad (2)$$

Equation 1 defines the Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation rate, Ψ , as the derivative of the surface buoyancy flux B with respect to potential density σ_2 . This describes how surface fluxes modify water masses along density classes.

In Equation 2, B combines the effects of heat and freshwater fluxes. The first term, which is the heat flux one, represents the impact of surface heat exchange, where α is the thermal expansion coefficient, Q the surface heat flux, and C_p the seawater heat capacity ($3992 \text{ J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$). The second term, the freshwater flux one, includes the haline contraction coefficient β , surface density σ_2 , normalized salinity s , and surface freshwater flux W . These terms together describe how buoyancy at the ocean surface is altered by temperature and salinity changes, driving water mass transformation.

For Q , we used `hfds`, the Downward Heat Flux at Sea Water Surface, in $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. We used the `wfo` CMIP6 variable, known as “Water Flux into Sea Water”, in $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ for W . The freshwater flux values for both `HadGEM3-GC31-LL` and `UKESM1-0-LL` were inconsistent with the other results of the study. Therefore, we applied a sign correction. The plots and maps presented in the Section 3.3 reflect this correction.

Figure 4: *Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation (SFWMT) annual rate for UKESM1-0-LL, averaged over 1970-2014.*

Two types of information can be interpreted from a SFWMT plot (Figure 4). The first one is the phenomenon of densification or lightening, depending on the sign of SFWMT value. The second one, which can be read by looking at the slope of the curve, is the water mass formation or destruction process.

In order to know if a water mass is formed or destroyed, we must look at the density gradient. For instance, UKESM1-0-LL has a positive value peak at $27.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Positive values correspond to densification. From 27.3 to $27.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, there is a loss of volume because each density class loses even more buoyancy than the class of values below. It means that there is a divergence and thus water mass destruction. On the contrary, there is formation of water masses between 27.5 and $28.0 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. It is thus associated with densification because the water mass is created by higher classes of density.

The analysis of the plot is the other way around for negative values, associated with lightening processes. There is a water mass formation between 26.0 and $27.1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and a destruction between 27.1 and 27.3 density units. It is associated with a buoyancy loss because the water mass is formed with lower classes of density.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Realism of dense water representation

The first step of this work is to investigate how well the models represent dense water. We evaluate the models by comparing them with observations. This evaluation aims at identifying the main biases and the models which manage to represent the water masses of interest. Therefore, we look at the simulated temperature and salinity, the variables defining the water masses, and we analyse if they overlap with the observed ones.

Thermohaline properties

The representation of AABW differs from one model to another (Figure 5a). UKESM1-0-LL is the only model for which the range of temperature and salinity values of AABW correspond to the observed ones. Four models are warmer than the observations (CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC31-LL and NESM3) and two are colder than the observations (CanESM5 and IPSL-CM6A-LR). NESM3 is the model that is furthest from observations with positive temperature biases reaching up to 2°C.

On the continental shelf, the temperature of ISW and HSSW is a distinctive feature compared to other water masses because it is defined as being below the surface freezing point (Figure 5b). Nonetheless, only 3 of the 7 models (UKESM1-0-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and HadGEM3-GC31-LL) have waters below the surface freezing point. CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3 and NESM3 are warmer than the observations. For example, when looking at HSSW, the temperature difference between the observations and NESM3 reaches 3°C.

(a) Offshore (bathymetry > 600 m)

(b) On the continental shelf (bathymetry ≤ 600 m)

Figure 5: T - S plots in the Prydz Bay region for observations and simulations. The red boxes represent the observed properties of the water masses. The red arrows emphasize the points below the surface freezing point. Period of time: climatology averaged over 1981–2010.

Thermohaline biases at depth

Dense water resides at depth, therefore it is relevant to know the magnitude of temperature and salinity biases at this location (Figure 6). Note that we look here at the deepest observed level, which does not necessarily correspond to bathymetry.

UKESM1-0-LL has the smallest temperature bias compared to the observations. Four models have warmer values than the observations (CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3, IPSL-CM6A-LR and NESM3), in particular offshore. NESM3 is, among them, the one presenting the largest biases, with some areas on shelf exhibiting temperature values being more than 2°C above the observed ones. CanESM5 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL are generally colder offshore than observations.

The largest differences between simulated and observed salinity can be seen on the continental shelf. Three models are significantly fresher than observations (CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3, IPSL-CM6A-LR). For three others, the difference is less pronounced (CanESM5, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, UKESM1-0-LL). Finally, NESM3, which had the warmest bias, is saltier than the observations, both on the continental shelf and offshore.

For the next parts, we decide to dismiss the NESM3 model, which has the highest biases in terms of thermohaline properties and does not represent the water masses of interest.

(a) Temperature

(b) Salinity

Figure 6: Differences (Models - Observations) for the deepest observed layer, Period of time : averaged over 1981-2010, summer (January - February - March)

Exploring Mixed Layer Depth

During dense water formation, a lot of mixing occurs in deep convection layers and is often associated with high values of Mixed Layer Depth thickness.

Figure 7: *Mixed Layer Depth thickness, Period of time : 1970-2014, winter (July-August-September)*

CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3 have much deeper Mixed Layer Depth thickness values offshore compared to the observations, exceeding 200 m depth difference (Figure 8). These models are particularly overestimating deep convection.

On the continental shelf, most of the models (CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL) overestimate the Mixed Layer Depth thickness, see Figure 8. These coastal areas with high values of Mixed Layer Depth thickness could correspond to potential candidate polynyas but this hypothesis must be confirmed thanks to other metrics (sea ice concentration, sea ice thickness, sea ice production rate...).

Figure 8: *Mixed Layer Depth differences (Models - Observations), Period of time : averaged over 1970-2014, winter (July-August-September)*

3.2 Processes linked to dense water formation and export

In this part, we focus on the ability of models to represent the processes involved in the formation and export of dense water. We conduct a cross-comparison between models and set aside the observations. Regarding formation processes, our work aims at identifying potential candidate coastal polynyas in order to know if models create dense water in a realistic place. We also look at bottom metrics to see if the conditions at depth are consistent with the presence of AABW, consequently to its export.

Sea ice concentration

Figure 9: *Simulated sea ice concentration in Prydz Bay. Red boxes correspond to the potential location of respectively 1) Cape Darnley polynya ; 2) Mackenzie polynya ; 3) Davis polynya ; 4) Barrier polynya, Period of time : averaged over 1970-2014, winter (July - August - September)*

We focus on winter sea ice concentration because it is when it has its seasonal peak influence on dense water formation. Coastal polynyas are usually associated with areas of low sea ice concentration on the shelf. Thus, the locations highlighted with the red boxes on CanESM5 map (Figure 9) could be candidate polynyas, as the associated sea ice concentration values drop below 50%. These features are less pronounced for HadGEM3-GC31-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL, as sea ice concentration remains above 60%. EC-Earth3 and CNRM-CM6-1 present large areas of open water offshore that overlap with areas of high values of Mixed Layer Depth thickness noticeable on Figure 8.

Bottom properties

(a) Temperature

(b) Salinity

(c) Density

Figure 10: *Simulated bottom variables, Period of time : averaged over 1981-2010, annual climatology*

Figure 11: *Bottom conditions consistent with AABW definition, Period of time : averaged over 1981-2010, annual climatology*

We compare the values of temperature, salinity and density, the net effect of the two previous variables at depth.

According to the definition given in the introduction, AABW regional temperatures are below 0.1°C . Among the 6 models, 3 of them (CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL) have a warmer temperature than this threshold value (Figure 11). In terms of salinity, the three previously cited models are fresher on shelf. However, offshore, all 6 models have salinity conditions consistent with the AABW definition, in other words have salinity values offshore higher than 34.5 g/kg . AABW is defined as having density superior to 27.82 . CanESM5 and IPSL-CM6A-LR are the models with density values superior or equal this threshold.

Overall, based on the bottom properties maps (Figure 10), we can distinguish 2 main groups of models. CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL are the warmest and freshest on the continental shelf. The net effect of these 2 variables is a lower value of density compared to the other group of models (CanESM5, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL., which are colder. CanESM5, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL have thermohaline conditions consistent with the AABW definition but the three other models don't, salinity being the limiting condition on the shelf and temperature the one offshore.

3.3 Creation of dense water in the models

In the last part, our goal is to understand what are differences in the approaches of the climate centers regarding the representation of high latitude processes and dense water creation and export. The associated results and discussion parts include plots and existing literature review.

To refine our diagnosis of polynya presence, we look at sea ice production and thickness. Moreover, the age of the water masses gives information about the temporality of both water mass formation on the continental shelf and ventilation at depth after export.

Age tracers

Bottom seawater age since surface contact can give both information about the temporality of dense water formation on shelf and potential ventilation after export.

In the coastal region of Prydz Bay, HadGEM-GC31-LL and UKESM1-0-LL create the youngest water (approximately 125 years) and highest amount among the analysed models (Figure 12b). For CanESM5, among the four different AABW formation sites, Prydz Bay is the region with the weakest signals of young water being formed (Figure 12a). This signal is mostly in the area which corresponds to Cape Darnley polynya location. The sea water age since surface contact is approximately 1250 years for CanESM5 (Appendix 2b). IPSL-CM6A-LR areas of recently formed waters are mostly located at Cape Darnley polynya and Davis polynya level. The range of values of age since surface contact at bottom level is around 350 years (Appendix 2a).

In terms of abyssal ventilation, CanESM5 is the model that ventilates the least. When examining higher values of age since surface contact (see Appendix 2), a ventilation pattern becomes apparent, with at least one clear minimum observed in the Weddell Sea. Ventilation must be very weak but not null. IPSL-CM6A-LR shows one main ventilation source, coming from Ross Sea. For UKESM1-0-LL and HadGEM3-GC31-LL, Ross and Wedell seas seem to be the two main ventilation sites, not continuously interconnected.

None of the models exhibit strong open-ocean convection features, which suggests that the most significant AABW production mode is on the continental shelf.

(a) Southern Ocean (South of 60°S)

(b) Prydz Bay region

Figure 12: *Sea water age since surface contact at bottom depth, Period of time : averaged over 1970-2014, winter (July-August-September)*

Sea ice thickness

To investigate potential sites of dense water water formation, we examined sea ice thickness as a complement to sea ice concentration.

CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3 have large areas of low sea ice thickness offshore, see Figure 13). The four other models - CanESM5, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL - present signals of low sea ice thickness on the shelf, which could correspond to potential coastal polynyas, particularly pronounced for IPSL-CM6A-LR.

Figure 13: *Sea ice thickness, Period of time : averaged over 1970-2014, winter (July-August-September)*

Sea ice production

Sea ice production is another variable that we use to assess potential polynya signals, in addition to sea ice concentration and thickness.

(a) Southern Ocean (South of 60°S)

(b) Prydz Bay region

Figure 14: Sea ice production rate, Period of time : averaged over 1970-2014, winter (July-August-September)

The annual rate of sea ice growth from sea water results from the combination of two CMIP6 variables ; namely basal growth from sea water (sidmassgrowthbot) and frazil growth in open water (sidmassgrowthfrazil).

IPSL-CM6A-LR exhibits the strongest coastal signal of sea ice growth from sea water on the shelf (Figure 2). This signal is weaker for EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC31-LL and UKESM1-0-LL, although they present a similar pattern. CNRM-CM6-1 has a different pattern, with higher values offshore (in the western part) compared to the other 5 models. This phenomenon is also noticeable when looking at the whole Southern Ocean (below 60°S), CNRM-CM6-1 exhibiting higher values of sea ice growth from sea water compared to the other models, with really low signals offshore.

Surface buoyancy fluxes

The surface buoyancy flux is the result of two different terms: a heat and a freshwater term. Among these two types of surface buoyancy fluxes, the freshwater one is responsible for the majority of the resulting Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation in our region of interest (see Appendix 3). In this study, positive values of surface freshwater fluxes correspond to a freshwater gain for the ocean (precipitation, river runoff and ice melt). Negative values correspond to freshwater being removed from the ocean (evaporation, freezing, sea-ice export).

Five out of six models - CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL - have the same pattern, exhibiting negative values on shelf and positive offshore (Figure 15). These negative values could be potentially explained by sea ice formation processes. IPSL-CM6A-LR and HadGEM3-GC31-LL have the strongest signals, with values reaching $-2.0 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, occuring over the largest spatial extent. CanESM5 presents overall slightly negative freshwater flux values both offshore and shelf, except on several localised shelf areas.

Figure 15: *Freshwater fluxes in Prydz Bay region, Negative (resp. positive) values : loss (resp. gain) of freshwater for the ocean, Period of time : 1970-2014, annual climatology*

Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation (SFWMT)

None of the models create waters in the range of density that could correspond to shelf waters given the water mass definitions displayed in Table 1 (Figure 16). The models creating water masses in the highest density classes are HadGEM3-GC31-LL, ISPL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL. The transformation rate reaches 1.25 Sv.

The other models - CanESM5, CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3 do not create waters associated with buoyancy gain above $27.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. For CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3, the transformations in the highest range of densities are towards buoyancy loss. There is creation of water masses with waters of lower density values, whereas waters with higher density values are destroyed.

The patterns described are mostly the same for the Southern Ocean (below 60°S) and for Prydz Bay, although the transformation rate values are much higher - sometimes ten times higher - for the Southern Ocean.

(a) Southern Ocean (South of 60°S)

(b) Prydz Bay region

Figure 16: *SFWMT* (Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation) rate (*Sv*) in density coordinates ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)

Chapter 4

Summary and discussion

In this study, we focused on 7 models from CMIP6 that have NEMO as their ocean component. We first evaluated their ability to represent dense water and shelf properties, by comparing them with WOA observations in the region of Prydz Bay.

We found that, in terms of thermohaline properties, the only model to have AABW properties that fall within the observed range is UKESM1-0-LL. CanESM5 and IPSL-CM6A-LR have AABW properties that are too cold. EC-Earth3 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL are slightly too warm and too fresh and CNRM-CM6-1 and NESM3 are far too warm, of the order of 2°C in certain locations. In terms of shelf water properties (ISW and HSSW), once again UKESM1-0-LL is the most skilled in reproducing water mass properties that align well with the observations. IPSL-CM6A-LR and HadGEM3-GC31-LL show a presence of waters close to or just below surface freezing point and all the other models fail to represent dense shelf waters. The finding that UKESM1-0-LL is able to reproduce ISW properties is somewhat surprising given that the model does not explicitly simulate ocean-ice shelf interactions and suggests that a sophisticated parameterization for ice shelf melt must have been employed.

To investigate further the connection between shelf and offshore, we then compared the skill of the 7 models in representing deep water properties by comparing the thermohaline values at the deepest observed level (not necessarily the bottom). We found once again that the smallest biases exist for UKESM1-0-LL. HadGEM3-GC31-LL and CanESM5 are too warm on the shelf and too cold offshore but with relatively small salinity biases, and all the others have a warm bias with NESM3 biases exceeding 2°C in temperature and 0.25g/kg in salinity. CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3 and IPSL-CM6A-LR all have large fresh biases on the continental shelf indicating that the models are not correctly capturing sea ice conditions and thus HSSW production via polynya activity.

To further explore the presence of deep convection in the NEMO family of CMIP6, we undertook a comparison with the Mixed Layer Depth atlas published by Sallée et al. 2020 for the whole Prydz bay region. We found that all the models show the presence of deep mixed layers on the continental shelf in the approximate location of known polynya activity (Cape Darnley, MacKenzie, Davis and Barrier polynya), albeit with slightly too deep mixed layers. However, CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3 show large-scale deep convection offshore which is not present in the observations. Like in Heuzé (2021), we found that the models that convect the least and have little to no open-ocean convection tend to be the most accurate.

We cross-compared 6 of the models used to better understand the relationship between sea ice concentration, deep convection and identified thermohaline biases in the models. We did not include NESM3 in this cross-comparison due to its large biases.

We found that UKESM1-0-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and CanESM5 have the coldest bottom properties and most saline properties on the continental shelf, indicating that these three models are the most skilled in representing dense shelf water formation and export. These models satisfy the combined temperature and salinity condition consistent with the AABW definition. CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3 show the lowest densities on the continental shelf due to what appears to be a large fresh bias and in no places satisfy the bottom conditions known to be associated with AABW properties.

CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3 also show the lowest values of sea ice concentration offshore, associated with large areas of open water offshore, consistent with the areas of deep Mixed Layer Depth thickness. It highlights how ice cover modulates ocean interactions with the atmosphere and how open waters allow for deep mixing. The models present low sea ice concentration coastal signals that could be associated with candidate polynyas on the shelf. These signals are the strongest for CanESM5, CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth3. Nonetheless, CanESM5 is the only model exhibiting strong signs for candidate coastal polynyas without having large areas of open water offshore.

As a final step to better understand the transformation of surface waters to dense shelf waters and the subsequent export of these waters to form AABW, we then cross compared age-tracers, sea ice production, and buoyancy fluxes in the models, and computed the surface water mass transformation flux for the whole Prydz bay region.

We found that the highest amount of recently formed waters is exhibited by both HadGEM3-GC31-LL and UKESM1-0-LL, whereas CanESM5 displays the lowest amount among the 4 models. None of the models exhibit a clear open-ocean convection signal, thus it seems that their main production mode of waters is on the continental shelf. In terms of abyssal ventilation, the four models do ventilate but at different degrees. For HadGEM3-GC31-LL and UKESM1-0-LL, agesc values offshore correspond to the simulation duration and therefore might not indicate the real age of the water. It could be due to the fact that it is recommended “initializing age globally to zero at 1 January 1850 in the historical experiments, or at the start of any of the various scenario experiments” in Griffies et al. (2016). IPSL-CM6A-LR has more realistic values of agesc for AABW, around 400 years. The (very) high values of agesc for CanESM5 could be explained by low dense water formation and/or low communication between the shelf and the deep ocean.

ISPL-CM6A-LR has the highest annual rate of ice growth on the continental shelf. CNRM-CM6-1 exhibits high growth rates both inshore and offshore. However, for this model and also and EC-Earth3, the areas of high values of Mixed Layer Depth thickness and low sea ice concentration are associated with the lowest values of ice growth rate, suggesting that these areas of large-scale deep convection offshore are not associated with polynya activity and thus dense water formation.

In order to better understand the transformation of surface waters, we looked at surface buoyancy fluxes. Among the heat and freshwater components, freshwater plays a domi-

nant role in determining the total Surface Flux Water Mass Transformation (SFWMT) rate. Except for CanESM5, the 5 other models - CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL - present a similar pattern, a clear separation between offshore and shelf, and values associated with freshwater loss on the shelf, which could be due to sea ice formation. We can draw a parallel between these patterns and the bathymetry, with a clear offshore/shelf contrast.

Regarding SFWMT, in Prydz Bay region, HadGEM3-GC31-LL, IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL create the densest water mass among the 6 models. Nonetheless, the highest associated density value is 27.5 kg.m^{-3} , which is lower than the values expected according to the definition of HSSW and AABW from the literature (Murakami et al. 2023). CNRM-CM6-1 and EC-Earth-3 have negative transformation rate values in the highest range of density. It means that the associated surface water mass transformation is toward lower density values and thus not associated with dense water formation.

Finally, it is important to mention the several caveats of this study. We focused on the NEMO family of CMIP6 models and so this study does not provide exhaustive results for the whole of CMIP6 models. Moreover, in the first part, the evaluation of the models required the use of observations. The number of observations is limited, especially in winter and at full depth (Figure 3). The evaluation of properties at depth, during the peak seasonal influence of the related processes can be biased by the sparsity of observational data.

In CMIP6 models, ice shelf cavities are closed and thus ocean-ice shelf interactions are not explicitly simulated. Without the presence of interactive ice shelves, it is very challenging to correctly represent the parent waters of AABW in coupled climate models. In terms of water mass realism, models that have paid attention to how this freshwater flux is represented —such as UKESM1-0-LL and IPSL-CM6A-LR — tend to better match observations. This can be achieved through the use of parameterizations like that developed by Mathiot et al. (2017), as well as through active tuning of Southern Ocean conditions. Based on the available model documentation, we found no evidence of targeted Southern Ocean or ice-shelf parameterizations for CanESM5 (Swart et al. 2019), and no explicitly documented Southern Ocean tuning for EC-Earth3 (Döscher et al. 2022). In contrast, HadGEM3-GC31-LL and UKESM1-0-LL include explicit sea ice tuning in polar regions, particularly via their implementation of the CICE5.1.2 model (Ridley et al. 2018), and CNRM-CM6-1 includes efforts to reduce temperature and salinity biases in the Southern Ocean (Voltaire et al. 2019). IPSL-CM6A-LR also underwent tuning for high-latitude processes, including adjustments to surface schemes relevant to Antarctic climate (Boucher et al. 2020 ; Mignot et al. 2021).

Chapter 5

Conclusion and outlook

In this study, we investigated the properties associated with the representation of dense water, with processes linked to dense water formation, their subsequent export and the transformation of surface waters to dense shelf waters.

IPSL-CM6A-LR and UKESM1-0-LL are the most skilled models in accurately representing these water masses and the associated processes. Overall, models that convect the most, especially offshore, tend to be the least accurate. As CMIP7 is coming up, over-active convection and absence of ocean-ice shelf interaction appear to be the main reasons affecting dense water realism in Prydz Bay.

In this study, we focused on a limited set of models with a horizontal resolution of 1° , and on a specific region. Given that dense water formation and export are sensitive to model resolution (Schmidt et al. 2025), future work could explore these processes using higher-resolution models and a broader spatial domain, including other Antarctic regions or the entire Southern Ocean.

Appendix

Figure 1: *Bathymetry maps.*

(a) Colorbar adapted to IPSL-CM6A-LR range of values

(b) Colorbar adapted to CanESM5 range of values

Figure 2: Sea water age since surface contact at bottom depth, Period of time : average over 1970-2014, winter (July-August-September)

Figure 3: Heat fluxes in Prydz Bay region, Negative (resp. positive) values : loss (resp. gain) of heat for the ocean, Period of time : 1970-2014, annual climatology.

Bibliography

- Blanckensee, S., D. Gwyther, B. Galton-Fenzi, K. Gunn, L. Herraiz-Borreguero, K. Ohshima, E. Portela Rodriguez, A. Post, and H. Bostock (2024). “A review of the oceanography and Antarctic Bottom Water formation offshore Cape Darnley, East Antarctica”. In: *Journal Of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 129.10, e2024JC021251. DOI: 10.1029/2024JC021251.
- Boucher, O. et al. (2020). “Presentation and evaluation of the IPSL-CM6A-LR climate model”. In: *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*. DOI: 10.1029/2019MS002010.
- Döscher, R. et al. (2022). “The EC-Earth3 Earth system model for CMIP6”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development*. DOI: 10.5194/gmd-15-2973-2022.
- Griffies, S. M., G. Danabasoglu, P. J. Durack, A. J. Adcroft, V. Balaji, C. W. Böning, E. P. Chassignet, E. Curchitser, J. Deshayes, H. Drange, B. Fox-Kemper, P. J. Gleckler, J. M. Gregory, H. Haak, R. W. Hallberg, P. Heimbach, H. T. Hewitt, D. M. Holland, T. Ilyina, J. H. Jungclaus, Y. Komuro, J. P. Krasting, W. G. Large, S. J. Marsland, S. Masina, T. J. McDougall, A. J. G. Nurser, J. C. Orr, A. Pirani, F. Qiao, R. J. Stouffer, K. E. Taylor, A. M. Treguier, H. Tsujino, P. Uotila, M. Valdivieso, Q. Wang, M. Winton, and S. G. Yeager (2016). “OMIP contribution to CMIP6: experimental and diagnostic protocol for the physical component of the Ocean Model Intercomparison Project”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 9, pp. 3231–3296. DOI: 10.5194/gmd-9-3231-2016.
- Heuzé, C. (2021). “Antarctic Bottom Water and North Atlantic Deep Water in CMIP6 models”. In: *Ocean Science* 17, pp. 59–90. DOI: 10.5194/os-17-59-2021.
- Jia, R., M. Chen, H. Pan, J. Zeng, J. Zhu, X. Liu, M. Zheng, and Y. Qiu (2022). “Freshwater Components Track the Export of Dense Shelf Water from Prydz Bay, Antarctica”. In: *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 196, p. 105023. DOI: 10.1016/j.dsr2.2022.105023.
- Jin, J., A. J. Payne, and C. Y. S. Bull (2024). “Current reversal leads to regime change in Amery Ice Shelf cavity in the twenty-first century”. In: *EGUsphere [preprint]*. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-2024-1287.

- Locarnini, R. A., A. V. Mishonov, O. K. Baranova, J. R. Reagan, T. P. Boyer, D. Seidov, Z. Wang, H. E. Garcia, C. Bouchard, S. L. Cross, C. R. Paver, and D. Dukhovskoy (2024). “World Ocean Atlas 2023, Volume 1: Temperature”. In: ed. by A. Mishonov. DOI: 10.25923/54bh-1613.
- Madec, G. and the NEMO System Team (2024). “NEMO Ocean Engine Reference Manual”. In: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1464816.
- Mathiot, P., A. Jenkins, C. Harris, and G. Madec (2017). “Explicit representation and parametrised impacts of under ice shelf seas in the z^* coordinate ocean model NEMO 3.6”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 10, pp. 2849–2874. DOI: 10.5194/gmd-10-2849-2017.
- Mignot, J. et al. (2021). “The tuning strategy of the IPSL-CM6A-LR”. In: *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*. DOI: 10.1029/2020MS002340.
- Mohrmann, M., C. Heuzé, and S. Swart (2021). “Southern Ocean Polynyas in CMIP6 Models”. In: *The Cryosphere* 15, pp. 4281–4304. DOI: 10.5194/tc-15-4281-2021.
- Murakami, M., A. Nummelin, B. Galton-Fenzi, and P. Uotila (2023). “Water Mass Transformations Within Antarctic Coastal Polynyas of Prydz Bay from Clustered Drifters”. In: DOI: 10.22541/essoar.169228932.20068035/v2.
- Pellichero, V., J. B. Sallée, C. C. Chapman, and S. M. Downes (2018). “The southern ocean meridional overturning in the sea-ice sector is driven by freshwater fluxes”. In: *Nature Communications* 9, p. 1789. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-018-04101-2.
- Post, A. L., B. K. Galton-Fenzi, M. J. Riddle, L. Herraiz-Borreguero, P. E. O’Brien, M. A. Hemer, A. McMinn, D. Rasch, and M. Craven (2014). “Modern sedimentation, circulation and life beneath the Amery Ice Shelf, East Antarctica”. In: *Continental Shelf Research* 78, pp. 10–23. DOI: 10.1016/j.csr.2013.10.010.
- Reagan, J. R., D. Seidov, Z. Wang, D. Dukhovskoy, T. P. Boyer, R. A. Locarnini, O. K. Baranova, A. V. Mishonov, H. E. Garcia, C. Bouchard, S. L. Cross, and C. R. Paver (2024). “World Ocean Atlas 2023, Volume 2: Salinity”. In: ed. by A. Mishonov. DOI: 10.25923/70qt-9574.
- Ridley, J. K. et al. (2018). “The sea ice model component of HadGEM3-GC3.1”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development*. DOI: 10.5194/gmd-11-713-2018.
- Sallée, J. B., V. Pellichero, C. Akhoudas, E. Pauthenet, L. Vignes, S. Schmidtko, A. Naveira Garabato, P. Sutherland, and M. Kuusela (2020). “Fifty-year changes of the

world ocean's surface layer in response to climate change". In: *Nature* 591, pp. 592–598. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4073173.

Schmidt, C., A. K. Morrison, M. H. England, W. Aguiar, and A. H. Gibson (2025). "Sensitivity of Antarctic Bottom Water Formation and Export to Horizontal Model Resolution". In: *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 17.7, e2024MS004621. DOI: 10.1029/2024MS004621.

Swart, N. C. et al. (2019). "The Canadian Earth System Model version 5 (CanESM5.0.3)". In: *Geoscientific Model Development*. DOI: 10.5194/gmd-12-4823-2019.

Vogt, L., J.-B. Sallée, and C. de Lavergne (2024). "Stratification and overturning circulation are intertwined controls on ocean heat uptake efficiency in climate models". In: *EGUsphere [preprint]*. DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-2024-3442.

Voltaire, A. et al. (2019). "Evaluation of CMIP6 DECK experiments with CNRM-CM6-1". In: *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*. DOI: 10.1029/2019MS001683.